

OCR at Service of Industry Digitalization

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1. Introduction

Each day, the world produces 2.5 quintillion bytes of data. Almost 80% of this data is unstructured, primarily in the form of text. The unstructured data is the bulk of information. In the era of digitalization, society is moving from paper-based document to digital data. The acquisition of no digital records has become a priority that cannot be ignored anymore. This challenge becomes more complicated when it involves handwritten data. Optical character recognition (OCR) is the set of techniques used to convert images of typed, handwritten or printed text into digital text. By following new technologies, industries need to establish a new culture of data management to better structure and to have profit of these generated data. This leads to move from an expertise-driven approach to a data-driven approach that will change the way to work and live.

2. Aim

By succeeding in new paper-less industrial environment, the aim of digitalization is to handle huge of textual data and to convert into digital format. By moving from a document-based approach to a data based approach, company can leverage their experience and enrich the quality of their work.

3. Material and methods

Applied artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning and natural language processing are the core of data digitalization. These solutions enable industry to solve business and real-world challenges across several domains, where AI is at the service of people and industry providing opportunities for time and cost savings.

Various existing machine-learning techniques for OCR have been developed and published as open source. Big progress has been accomplish thanks to the large volumes of data available. The most effective methods are based on:

- Deep Learning Cloud OCR and text detection with OpenCV
- Google Vision for OCR
- MicroSoft computer-vision

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- Amazone Rekognition
- Local OCR
- PyTesseract
- OCRmyPDF

The scanned images is analysed for light and dark areas in order to identify each alphabetic letter or numeric digit. The advanced prediction model estimates the probability for each character and classify their recognition.

4. Results

The OCR model developed has an accuracy of 99% for typed text and 94% for handwritten text. Before there is an example of text extraction by using our OCR model for a piece of scan image.

It is important to notify that the accuracy depends on the quality of writer in the case of handwritten text. Further, image for OCR have to fill-fill a certain quality level. The better the quality of the original source image, the higher the accuracy of OCR.

5. Conclusions

By the combination of OCR model and “bespoke” interface, the industry 4.0 can establish an efficient transition to the digital era keeping in mind the necessity of the "paper-less" long term goal. While friendly interfaces allow company to generate data directly interpretable from the machine, OCR represents the solution for all the knowledge accumulated by company inside past documents. The digitalization will guarantee to the new version of industry to be competitive in a job market where excellence is essential.

6. Keywords

OCR, Data Digitalization, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Data Analytics, Data Mining, Machine Learning and Data Science.

Author biography

Nassara ELHADJI ILLE GADO has completed her PhD from the University of Technology of Troyes (UTT, France) in Machine Learning for high dimensional data in 2017. She has published four conferences papers at ICMLA and ICPRAM. After one year as assistant professor at UTT, She is currently working as Data Scientist within the cell of innovation of Assystem Energy & Infrastructure.